

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

D4.1: Report on technical guidance and examples for data processing and modularization

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The [ACT4CAP27 project](#) addresses the increasing complexity of sustainability models by establishing the ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal, a shared IT infrastructure under Work Package 4 (WP4) in the following referred to as “Accelerator platform”. This portal facilitates modular, automated, and version-controlled data flows, supporting WP2 (sustainability coverage), WP3 (agro-food system models), WP5 (modeling infrastructure), and WP6 (EU agri-food policy assessments post-2027). The platform emphasizes automation, transparency, scalability, and interoperability, aligning with FAIR data principles to streamline data processing and model-based scenario analysis.

The technical pipeline integrates raw data from public or partner sources, stored and versioned in the Accelerator data repository using Data Version Control (DVC) alongside Git. Standardized scripts clean and transform data into model-ready formats, enabling execution on the Accelerator platform or externally, with outputs harmonized via the AgMIP template for interoperability. The Accelerator supports modularity, reproducibility, scalability, and seamless integration of new datasets and models. Version control ensures traceability, with DVC managing large datasets and Git handling code and metadata. The Accelerator allows flexible job flows, defining job sequences for automated processing, and supports a well-defined software stack for reproducible outcomes. The AgMIP template, evolving into the ACT4CAP27 template, ensures consistent model outputs, validated for downstream use. This infrastructure enables transparent, policy-relevant results for sustainability analysis and visualization. A comprehensive online documentation with use-cases is available [here](#).

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the ACT4CAP27, the increasing complexity and interconnectivity of sustainability models necessitate a more systematic, scalable, and transparent approach to data management. WP4 plays a critical role in enabling this by establishing a shared IT infrastructure — the **ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal** — that supports modular, automated, and version-controlled data flows across work packages, in particular for WP2 (Coverage of economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of food systems), WP3 (Model structures for representation of agro-food systems and policies), WP5 (Modelling infrastructure and capacity building), and WP6 (Assessments of EU agri-food policies post 2027).

This document provides technical guidance for consortium partners and module developers who are contributing new data processing routines and model developments to the broader modelling architecture that will allow us to link multiple models and run in a flexible manner integrated scenarios. This deliverable outlines how data is stored and versioned, how processing scripts and models/modules should be structured and maintained, and how scripted processing flows for scenario assessments can be integrated on the Accelerator platform.

Key motivations for this modular and platform-oriented approach in ACT4CAP27 include:

- **Automation:** Reducing manual effort in fetching, cleaning, and transforming data by developing reusable, well-documented scripts that are shared across partners and eventually also outside the consortium.
- **Transparency:** Ensuring that all inputs, processes, and outputs are traceable and open for review, in line with FAIR data principles.
- **Scalability:** Supporting the iterative development of new modules, model linkages, and data sources as the project evolves.
- **Interoperability:** Harmonizing data formats and standards to ensure compatibility across diverse models, including those focused on land use, emissions, biodiversity, and socio-economic indicators.

By following the guidance provided in this document, module developers can ensure that their contributions are properly linked with the Accelerator platform — enabling streamlined data processing, model-based scenario analysis, and the generation of up-to-date, policy-relevant results for analysis and visualization. A comprehensive online documentation can be accessed via the Accelerator platform [here](#) including detailed hands-on [use-cases](#).

2. NOMENCLATURE

To ensure a shared understanding across a multidisciplinary consortium, this section defines key terms and concepts used in this report.

Table 1 Common vocabulary and its meaning.

Term	Meaning
Accelerator	Platform for ACT4CAP27 model processing, integration, and data collaboration.
Stack	The stack of software on top of which code or binaries run: operating system, libraries, language runtime, and packages.

Routine	A specification of code/software to process on the Accelerator together with a specification of the software stack on top of which to run it.
Job	An instance of a routine that is running or has run.
Jobflow	A graphical or scripted definition of the dependencies and sequencing that determines in which order jobs are run.
Model	A research model. A model can be captured as a monolithic routine that is run as a job. Alternatively, a model can be divided into stages captured as routines that are run as jobs sequenced by a job flow.
Module	Processing code/software providing functionality subservient to modeling or model integration. A module is captured in a routine and run as a job.

3. TECHNICAL PIPELINE

The technical pipeline outlines an approximate end-to-end flow of data processing and model integration within the project’s infrastructure, as illustrated in the Figure 1 below. It operationalizes the link between **Task 4.1** (Database and Data Processing Modules) and **Task 4.2** (Computational Framework), anchored by the **ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal**.

Figure 2 Generic overview of the technical pipeline.

At its core, the technical pipeline is designed to cater for two main use-cases: The first one begins with **raw data** sourced from public databases or partner contributions. These datasets are stored and version-controlled in the Accelerator data repository, ensuring traceability and reproducibility. Using a set of open-access, standardized processing scripts, the data is cleaned, transformed, and harmonized into model-/module-ready formats. In the second use case, the pre-compiled data enters the model execution phase. These models may run either directly on the Accelerator platform or externally, depending on their technical requirements and institutional ownership. Regardless of location, the models produce standardized outputs — such as those formatted via the [AgMIP template](#) — and relevant to various sustainability indicators (e.g., land use, emissions, biodiversity). The Accelerator platform supports automated ingestion of these outputs into other modules, collecting back additional indicators e.g. for biodiversity, pollution or health, and inserting them to the common output template. This ensures that model results, whether from internal or external sources, are interoperable and can be stored, compared, and visualized consistently within the platform. Ultimately, this enables integrated assessment workflows, transparent result sharing, and streamlined comparison across modules and scenarios.

This structured pipeline supports several key principles:

- **Modularity:** Each stage can be updated or replaced independently.
- **Reproducibility:** Through version control, logging, and open script repositories.
- **Interoperability:** Via common data formats and metadata standards.
- **Scalability:** Allowing new modules, models, and datasets to be integrated seamlessly.

Details on how **to implement and operationalize the two use cases** depicted in Figure 1 can be found in the online documentation:

- **Use Case 1:** Raw FAOSTAT Data to Model Input, technical example for Task 4.1
- **Use Case 2:** Model Output to Validated Indicators, technical example for Task 4.2

3.1. Impromptu Work Versus Consolidation

Before code runs, data has been validated, and insight and confidence emerge, impromptu work needs doing: experimentation, initial development, testing, and debugging. Such impromptu work typically constitutes the bulk of the effort. The guidance below should not be misconstrued as prohibiting or inhibiting impromptu work.

Quite the reverse: the freedom of action on a client machine and the flexibility of the interactive web interface of the Accelerator both support and invite impromptu work. Do experiment, perform initial development, and test and debug with gusto without feeling bound by the constraints of the guidance below. But with time, things will get more serious. Significant change will need to be consolidated into a form that others rely on; that others should be able to reproduce; or will be part of a publication. It is then crucial to engage in careful version control and data management.

The guidance below details how to perform [version control and data management](#) in conjunction with modularized processing while consolidating significant change for re-use, reproducibility, and publication, in the context of the ACT4CAP27 technical pipeline.

3.2. Version Control and Data Management

The **Accelerator Platform** includes a robust data repository designed to support handling of data in a version-controlled and well-managed manner. It is highly scalable, up to petabytes of data, and enables consistency and traceability throughout the data lifecycle.

Version control of data is managed using **DVC** (Data Version Control) tooling, which works alongside **Git** (preferred) or other version control systems for code. The Accelerator provides DVC with a storage backend that allows for quick access to big data when processing on the Accelerator. It also provides a means to upload or download carefully versioned data from or to a client machine for testing or processing there. From a client machine, users can either create a new Git repository or clone an existing one and data-enable it with DVC:

- When setting up a new repository, code and configuration are stored via Git and managed with regular [Git workflows](#), while data is stored via DVC in the Accelerator data repository with only small DVC mapping files stored in the Git repository. Metadata is stored in Git adjacent to the mapping files when not embedded in the data files.

- Such joint management of code, data, metadata, and configuration under version control ensures that these are mutually consistent for a given release.
 - Users can obtain a DVC storage URL via the Accelerator web interface.
- When [cloning](#) a DVC-enabled Git repository, the mapping to the remote DVC storage is already configured and large data can be selectively downloaded for modification or processing.
 - Selective downloading makes handling big data practical.

When using a DVC-enabled repository, users can add new data or modify or delete existing data within a local workspace. Once changes are made, they can be committed along with a commit message. These updates are applied to a local cache that is synchronized with the remote Accelerator data repository, thereby ensuring efficient tracking and versioning of modifications.

Given a [commit](#), [tag](#), or [release](#) of a DVC-enabled Git repository, the Accelerator compute platform or any client machine with sufficient resources can retrieve the code, data, metadata, and configuration and produce or reproduce outputs relative to a well-defined and versioned set of inputs.

Two default places are provided to host the DVC-enabled Git repositories under an ACT4CAP27 banner:

- An [ACT4CAP27 organization](#) on GitHub.
- An [ACT4CAP27 group](#) on the IIASA GitLab instance.

Pre-defined modules are provided for [pulling data from DVC](#) and [pushing data to DVC](#). These can be placed before and after a model in a jobflow to provision input from version control and consolidate output to version control.

3.3. Raw Data

Raw data is typically sourced as a partner contribution or from a third party such as [FAOSTAT](#). This presents several challenges:

- The website or data repository of the third party may not be available at all times.
- With time, data sets may disappear or be updated.
- The data may be very large and hence difficult to handle.
- Downloading the data may take a long time and might be error prone.

To handle raw data in a well-managed manner, it is therefore necessary to download it and place it under version control (see above). The raw data can thereafter be reproducibly used via Git/DVC. A download script should be co-versioned in Git so that later an updated version of the same subset of data sets can easily be downloaded from the third party website or data repository, and placed under version control as an additional commit, tag, or release. It is good practice to separate the configuration of the download script from the code as a separate file containing default configuration settings (for example key-value settings), and co-commit that configuration file.

When the raw data is very large, the download can be performed one data set at a time via a client machine, storing each dataset via DVC in turn. When even individual datasets are too large for the

client machine, the download script can be scheduled on the **Accelerator Platform** (see below) where sufficient storage resources are available.

Once committed to Git/DVC storage, a particular version of the raw data can be quickly made available for processing on the Accelerator, and can be downloaded with relative robustness to a client machine for processing there.

3.4. Input Data

Making raw data usable as input for a model may require cleanup, aggregation, relabeling, projection, and other transformations. When such processing is quick, the model can directly use the raw data as input and perform the needed transformations as part of its regular initialization operations.

Typically, raw data is large so that its transformation to usable model input data takes considerable time. Moreover, raw data tends to be updated only infrequently. In such a circumstance, it makes sense to separately transform the raw data to model input data, and place that input data under Git/DVC version control (see above) for model use.

At this stage, it is typically necessary to perform quality control by previewing and validating the transformed data. Any visualization or validation scripts used to this end should also be placed under version control for future re-use. Alternatively, the built-in visualisation and [validation features of the Accelerator platform](#) or interactive tools such as data viewers can be purposed.

Ensure that the resulting Git/DVC repository holds the following:

- DVC mapping files for the input data resulting from the transformation.
 - o With the actual data [pushed to DVC storage](#).
- Scripting to retrieve the raw data from its Git/DVC repository.
- Transformation scripts.
- Visualisation and validation quality control scripts, if any.
- Separate configuration files, ideally.
 - o For example, containing default values for the repository URL and commit ID or tag of the raw data.
- Documentation, at least a small README file.

By committing the above-listed mutually consistent set of files to the Git/DVC repository of the input data, the input data and its transformation become reusable and reproducible in a well-managed manner. The commit can be tagged or released with a name reflecting the version of the raw data that was transformed. Past versions can then be easily retrieved.

3.5. Intermediate and Output Data

Complex models may have stages that each take a long time to run. Some stages may need to run repeatedly or in parallel, for example modeling a set of scenarios with different parameters. In such a context it makes sense to have a prior stage place its output of intermediate data under Git/DVC version control (see above) for use and reuse as input to the next stage. That next stage can then be run independently, in a loop or in parallel on the Accelerator (see below) or a client machine.

Similarly, outputs of modules or models can serve as intermediate data to be passed as input to a model that performs the next stage of processing. And then there is output data of models to be

subjected to analysis. In all these instances, placing the data under Git/DVC versions control together with the artifacts needed for reproduction of the processing performed by the stage, module, or model provides considerable benefits: it encourages modularity by decoupling interdependent model stages and modules; provides freedom of scheduling (where, when, again); and enables later reproduction of results in piecemeal fashion.

3.6. Processing on a Well-Defined Stack

The **Accelerator Platform** provides a **processing capability** that can run pre-specified **routines** as **jobs** orchestrated via a **jobflow**. This enables on-Accelerator execution of automated sequences of modules, models, and model stages. Obvious benefits are:

- Users can collaborate on setting up and monitoring processing via a shared platform.
- Far more memory, disk, and compute resources are available to processing on the Accelerator than are present on a typical client machine.
- More formal processing can substitute for ad-hoc manual work on a client machine.

A not so obvious advantage is that the software stack on which processing occurs can be well-defined. This is crucial for reproducibility since the outcome of processing depends on the stack on which code runs. This stack includes the operating system, libraries, language runtime, and language packages needed to make a script run. The software stack typically varies from client machine to client machine, leading to possible differences in processing outcomes. Hence, when defining a routine, the Accelerator provides three ways to specify a well-defined software stack on which to run the code:

- 1) Selection of a stack from a library of pre-defined stacks.
- 2) Providing a build specification (a **Dockerfile**) of a container with the stack. The Accelerator will build the container before dispatching a job.
- 3) Providing a pre-built container image with the stack and code.

This is **optional**. Users may choose to **export well-versioned, model-ready input data** from the Accelerator data repository, run their models **outside** the Accelerator framework, and later return to the platform to upload and process the **model outputs**, continuing the rest of the pipeline within the Accelerator environment. But then users are obliged to tightly manage the stack on the client machine.

3.7. AgMIP Template

We expect **model outputs** to be **harmonized and consistent**, ensuring they can be confidently consumed by subsequent modules in the pipeline.

To achieve this, we define a set of structural and formatting rules—collectively referred to as a **dataset template**—which all model outputs must adhere to. For our initial use case, this ruleset is known as the **AgMIP Template** as used in other projects like BrightSpace and Lamasus. While a defined standard exists, the template is **flexible and can be amended** as project requirements evolve. The initial template provides the “default” reporting of most important e.g. variables, items, regions etc. Throughout a project it is typically amended to provide e.g. additional or more granular results across indicators, tailored to the research question and

scenario analysis performed. For example, more nutrient related indicators could be included in the template or additional regional breakdown of the results.

The dataset template is stored as a reusable **entity on the Accelerator platform** and is utilized by a dedicated **dataset validator routine**. Before a model output proceeds to the next stage in the pipeline, its output is validated against this template. If validation is successful, the dataset is tagged in the Accelerator Data Repository with a **template name mark**, indicating compliance.

3.8. Final ACT4CAP27 template

The AgMIP template will be evolved into the final ACT4CAP27 template with an extended range of indicators and its own dedicated validator. The Accelerator platform supports this effort by allowing easy addition and editing of template fields.

<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

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